

**EFFECTS OF POSITIVE PARENTING ON THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE
OF SELECTED LEARNERS IN A PRIVATE SCHOOL
IN LOPEZ, QUEZON**

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Effects of Positive Parenting on the Academic Performance of Selected Learners in a Private School in Lopez, Quezon

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the Effects of Positive Parenting in the Academic Performance of Selected Learners in a Private School in Lopez, Quezon. The respondent's profile were examined as well do the influence of positive parenting in their academic performance to achieve the researcher's objective. The researcher used the questionnaire to establish the respondents' profiles and to evaluate the positive parenting in the academic performance to achieve their knowledge. This included 80 selected grade 10 student in Lopez, Quezon The described approach focuses on the source of data and informs the results, which showed that the majority of the respondents aged 15-16 and have a percentage of 80 % and the percentage of 17-18 20% the most respondents are female with the percnrtaage of 54% and the male id 46%. According to the result of Kruskal Walis H- test the null hypothesis was rejected. Parents can advise and encourage their student's academic achievement in school. To boost students' learning ability, teachers may assign a variety of school tasks. Learners may continue to use the learning approach to boost their self-esteem. Future researchers may conduct a similar study to elaborate on the substance of the learners using others.

Keywords: *attendance, academic performance behaviour, communication between parent's and teacher's positive parenting*

Introduction

Positive parenting is the term used to describe to how parents help their children learn both at home and in school. Helping with homework attending school functions and parents teacher conference taking part in decision making process and maintaining regular contact with the child's teacher are just few example of how this can be done.

Dingli(2015) Started that in order for the K-12 curriculum to be implemented under Rep Act 10533,Educational systems must prepare students for lifelong skills that will help them succeed in the workplace. Accordingly the department of Education envisions all students to be functionally literate equipped with life skills that will allows them to appreciate art and sport and instill desirable personal.

The presence of parents was particularly crucial when it came to teaching, according to the researcher. Without the parent, it was difficult to obtain excellent academic accomplishment. In everyday life, the student requires the aid, care, and supervision of his or her parents. Despite the experiences, the researcher realised that some students were observe enough to have their requirements met. It was also reported from other pupils that they experienced the same thing but were thankful in spite of their parents' absence.

With this, the researcher will look into the effects of parental involvement on students. As a researcher observed and experienced that some parents are not involved in school activities, and the majority of them do not bring their children to school, and the mother is the one who is constantly involved in their children's education. These observations and experiences prompted a study on parental involvement in students' education. The researcher aims to see if there are any major disparities in how parents view their children's education.

Parents are also responsible for educating and interacting with their children through school curricula via supervising homework and communicating with teachers (Holloway et al., 2008). Positive cooperation and communication between parents and schools encourage the development and academic success of children. Parents who engage in the education and academic success of their children at home and school are proactively involved in the process (Mytton et al., 2014). As a result of playing an active role in the academic process, parental interest and involvement can then serve as a cornerstone of motivation and can impact 3 the learning process and academic potential of their children at school (Durisic & Bunijevac, 2017). In addition to parental involvement within the family unit and home environment, parental involvement in school is also fundamental. All parents and schools should play a significant role in their children's academic success within both home and school settings. Researchers have articulated that parentschool partnerships can significantly impact school and academic success (Epstein, 2018).

Research Questions

This study determine the effects of positive parenting on the academic performance of selected learners in a private school in lopez, quezon. Specifically, it will seek to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of respondents in terms:
 - 1.1. age, and
 - 1.2. sex?
2. What are the effect of positive parenting on students education in terms of:

- 2.1. attendance,
- 2.2. behavior,
- 2.3. academic performance, and
- 2.4. communication between teacher and parents
3. Is there a significant difference on the perceive effect of positive parenting to the students education when respondents are grouped according to profile?

Literature Review

Positive Parenting

Hayee and Rizvi, Citation(2017). In Pakistan, functional parenting was studied on participants aged 17 and up, highlighting the importance of parenting styles even after the age of 18. This may be due to the social norm in the West, where children typically begin living independently once they reach the age of 18. In contrast, in a country like Pakistan, the responsibility of parenting does not end at the teen age. The offspring live with their parents even after 18 years, and parents used to direct and support them by seeing them as their burden.

Thus, when the terms "parent" or "carer" are used above, they refer to anyone who has a consistent contact with a child and is concerned about his or her well-being (Seay, Freysteinson, & McFarlane, 2014).

Gender disparities in research productivity have been extensively studied. One common reason for these disparities is that women bear larger child-rearing responsibilities. However, shifting societal dynamics around parenting have resulted in men adopting a more active role in parenting. This necessitates a more nuanced approach to understanding the relationship between parenting and productivity for both men and women. In addition to parental type, partnership status, and gender, we include an interaction term between gender and parental leave lengths to investigate whether the relationship between parental leave lengths and productivity varies by gender. We account for the number of children as well as the respondents' academic age, highest degree attained, employment sector, and primary subject. Gemma E. Derrick 2022

Positive Parenting Programme system impacts a wide range of child, parent, and family outcomes. Multiple search algorithms revealed relevant studies, which were done over a period of time and included quantitative analyses of the families. Moderator analyses were carried out using structural equation modelling. The risk of bias within and between studies was examined. Significant short-term effects were found for: children's social, emotional, and behavioural outcomes, According to Clin Psychol Rev (2014)

Attendance

Attendance rate is important because students are more likely to succeed in academics when they attend school consistently. Sheridan (2016), the varieties of involvement reported in the literature may also be classified as types of relationship parents school and or teacher and or have parents disconnected relationship parent involve and parents and teacher as partners. The home and school share duties and make decisions on how to best serve the child.

Alandejani and Almadani (2018) define academic performance as the improvement of a student's existing state of knowledge and skills, as reflected in their GPA, as well as the development of their personality and academic advancement from lower levels of study to higher levels of study.

Abulibcia (2014), a school-based management approach empowers school leaders, teachers, and other stakeholders, including parents, to participate in decision-making, resulting in improved academic performance for students due to increased parental and community participation in their children's education.

According to Sheridan Knoche and Edwards (2016), the varieties of involvement reported in the literature may also be classified as types of relationship parents school and or teacher and or have parents disconnected relationship parent involve and parents and teacher as partners. The home and school share duties and make decisions on how to best serve the child.

According to Besser S, Chik A (2014), a focus group of parents participated in a workshop that focused on the practise of reading aloud to their children in English in order to examine what parents may do to support their children with school-based needs for English learning. The findings indicate that while Hong Kong parents are involved in helping their children's English literacy development in a number of ways, they do not generally embrace culturally distinctive Western practises such as reading aloud, and that doing so may be challenging.

Behavior

Parent engagement in addressing challenging behavior across a variety of settings (e.g., school settings, community settings, in the home) Farver et al., 2013 stated that Two of its facets, parent goals and parents' academic involvement as perceived by students, are found to predict students' choices of goals. Perceived parent mastery goals are defined through parents' goal-related messages that emphasize and encourage self-improvement in school, whereas perceived parent performance goals are recognized in those messages that highly value displays of ability or interpersonal comparisons.

Pratisha Padmasri Deka (2016) conducted a study on parental involvement in higher education; voices of parents and students in pubkamrup college and patidarrang college, Kamrup district, to bring to light the views, both positive and negative, of parents and students on the desirability of parental involvement in higher education level. Education entails not just acquiring academic degrees, but also learning how to be a productive member of society, how to behave in social circumstances, how to solve everyday difficulties, and so much more. Parents play an important role in their children's education both in and out of the classroom. As a result, parents must accept the challenge and equip their children with the skills they will need in order to be successful in life.

Chik A (2014), a focus group of parents participated in a workshop that focused on the practise of reading aloud to their children in English in order to examine what parents may do to support their children with school-based needs for English learning. The findings indicate that while Hong Kong parents are involved in helping their children's English literacy development in a number of ways, they do not generally embrace culturally distinctive Western practises such as reading aloud, and that doing so may be challenging.

Bartolomme and Selangan (2015) state that Although Filipino parents of all socioeconomic backgrounds value education, They believe that their children's achievement is critical and are prepared to go to considerable measures to support them. Retention is a serious challenge in Philippine schools, as many pupils drop out. continue past elementary school.

The majority of studies on parental involvement in schooling, however, come from anglophone nations and use cross-sectional and correlational methods (Garbacz et al., 2017)

Academic Performance

Academic performance, intelligence, and other indicators of learning ability have been widely studied regarding their associations with criminal and antisocial behavior

Blair(2014)Filipino parents across all social class levels typically regard education as essential to their children's success and are willing to go to great lengths to help their children through school, retention is a major concern in Philippine schools, as many students do not continue past their elementary grades.

Castro,De Jesus, and Sabanal (2018) found no significant relationship between parental involvement and academic performance in the school of Cabatian Elementary School in this study that measured parental involvement as PTA meetings. financial support and academics, and grades are used to assess academic performance. They also concluded that even when parents were involved, it had no effect on the students' grades.

Tufail and Hussain (2014) did a study to establish the impact of parenting styles on academic achievement among postgraduate students in Pakistan. The study showed a negligible link between authoritative parenting style and students' academic achievement.

Basari.Alandejani and Almadani (2018) define academic performance as the improvement of a student's existing state of knowledge and skills, as reflected in their GPA, as well as the development of their personality and academic advancement from lower levels of study to higher levels of study.

Communication Between Parents and Teachers

Parent-teacher communication begins at the start of a school year and lasts until students move onto the next grade. Teachers and parents will make introductions and gradually establish a relationship based on what they have in common:

Abulibcia (2014), a school-based management approach empowers school leaders, teachers, and other stakeholders, including parents, to participate in decision-making, resulting in improved academic performance for students due to increased parental and community participation in their children's education.

Eric (2017), parental involvement refers to a parent's level of involvement in his or her children's education. Some schools encourage healthy parental involvement, yet some parents are hesitant to get involved in their children's education. It is supported in Western countries. There is, however, a body of research that investigates the impact of social and cultural factors, as well as the effects of parental involvement in and expectations of their children's development and learning.

Spungan (2014) state that parental involvement begins with the belief that all parents began in the development and progress of their own children. Pen Green centre for under fives and families parental involvement has always been an essential component of every teacher students school academic endeavor.

Henderson cited by(sampungang G.and SampunganR.2014) entitled a new wave of evidence, the Impact of school, Family, and community connections on studies Achievement, the authors state that most students at all levels elementary, middle, and high school-want their families to be more knowledge partners about schooling and are willing to take active roles in assisting communications between home and school on a regular basis.

Abulon and Saquilabon (2016) conducted research on enhancing academic performance through parental involvement strategies and discovered that intervintion facilitated parental involvement elicited a significant positive difference on pretest and post-test, which is an indicator of academic performance improvement. They also concluded that a parent-friendly environment and other reinforcement

strategies should be provided because they enhance academic performance.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a descriptive research method that aimed to systematically obtain information to describe a phenomenon, situation, or population. more specifically, the Effects of positive parental education in Lopez, Quezon. The researcher used a survey questionnaire as an instrument. Based on the survey's results, the researcher will be able to determine the details of the study.

According to Creswell (1994), the descriptive method of research is to gather information about the present existing condition. Since this study is focused on the perception or evaluation of the consultancy firm's effective human resource management, the descriptive method is the most appropriate method to use.

Respondents

Random sampling is a part of the sampling technique in which each sample has an equal probability of being chosen. A sample chosen randomly is meant to be an unbiased representation of the total population.

Eighty (80) students officially enrolled at Eastern Tayabas College Inc. located at Lopez, Quezon will be selected through Proportionate Sampling.

Instrument

The researcher prepared a research-made questionnaire which were validated by two experts.

Part I. of the questionnaire included the profile of the respondents. Part II of the questionnaire consisted the Effects of positive parental in the academic performance in the academic performance using the likert scale of; Strongly agree (SA) 5, Agree(A) 4, Moderately Agree (MA) 3, Disagree (D)2, and Strongly disagree (SD)1,Effects of Positive Parental on the Academic Performance of Selected Learners of Private School in Lopez, Quezon.

Procedure

Prior to the conduct of the study, the researcher sent a letter to the schools Principal and Adviser. Upon approval, the researcher administered the instrument to the target respondents.

To prevent being distracted by class conversation, the researcher administered the questionnaire during the time designated for empty time. The student response was given appropriate time to respond to the questions. Following data collection, the researcher gathered them in order to tally the scores and apply the statistical treatment to be used in the study.

The descriptive research method using likert scale was used in order to rate the effects of positive parental on the education of grade 10 learners. Data were gathered through "Proportionate Sampling" both male and female officially enrolled in the private school in Lopez, Quezon will be selected to fill the questionnaire. Data were gathered through face-to-face survey. Following the safety health protocols to prevent the spread of the virus.

Data Analysis

In this study, the researcher used be statistical measures to treat the collected data. All the data were carefully read and examined for analysis. They use be tallied and entered into a master list of the data collection sheet. Percentage and Frequency were used to interpret the profile of the respondents. To test the significant difference of three or more means, the researcher will use the Kruskal-Wallis for non-parametric test.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered the results of the statistical analysis done and interpretation of findings. These are presented in tables following the sequence of the specific research problem regarding the Effect of Positive Parenting on the Academic Performance of Selected Learners in Private School.

Table 1-2, shows the Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age and Sex. The percentage shows the results of the number of the profile of the respondents according to their frequency.

Table 1. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Age*

Age	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
15-16	64	80	1
17-18	16	20	2
Total	80	100%	

Table 1 present the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of Age, these consist the age of the respondents of the selected learners in private school, most of the respondent are 15-16 years old with the percentage of 80% while 16 respondents are 17-18 years old with the percentage of 20%.

Hayee and Rizvi, Citation (2017). functional parenting was examined on participants aged 17 and up, emphasising the significance of parenting techniques even after the age of 18. Even after 18 years, the children live with their parents, who used to direct and support them as if they were a burden.

The data implies that within the local of research conducted majority of grade 10 students are 15-16 years old.

Table 2. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Sex*

Sex	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Female	43	54	1
Male	37	46	2
Total	80	100%	

Table 2 presents the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of Sex, most of the respondents are female with the percentage of 53.75%.

The sample included 210 male and 292 female undergraduate university students. "There are some distinctive aspects of Pakistani culture that do not appear to be shared with Western culture." Furthermore, the approach of Pakistani researchers who included young people to analyse the impact of parenting on the personality and behaviour of their offspring supports the selection of the age sample for the. Current research (e.g., Ahmed & Bhutto, Citation2016;)

This higher participation rate among female students is significantly associated with better to the finale grades and to supported learning that may be more prevailent in female majority classes.

Table 3. *Positive Parenting on the academic performance in terms of Attendance*

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Help me to increase my self-efficiency.	4.37	SA	3
2. Encourage me to attend class regularly.	4.48	SA	1.5
3. Assist me in maximizing my time in school	4.3	MA	4
4. Allow me to participate in extra-curricular.	4.48	SA	1.5
5. Keep an eye on my social awareness...	4.33	SA	5
Average Mean	4.39	SA	

Legend: Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1.0-1.80; Disagree (D) = 1.81-2.60 Agree (A) = 2.62-3.40 Moderately Agree(MA) = 3;41-4.20, Strongly Agree (SA) 4.21-5

Table 3 presents the Effect of Positive Parenting on the Academic Performance in terms of Attendance. The highest mean 4.48, allowed to participate in extracurricular and encouraged to attend class regularly with verbal interpretation Strongly Agree, While the lowest mean 4.3 Assist in maximizing time in school with the verbal interpretation Moderately Agree.

Leijten et al. (2017); Ozbek et al. (2018). If intervention uptake in research studies is low under generally favourable conditions, this signals a potentially major challenge for scale-up outside the research environment, which involves taking interventions to broader populations under less monitored and sometimes underfunded conditions. As a result, it is critical to investigate attendance rates and their drivers, as well as the influence of parental programming on those who really stick to them.

According to the results of the respodence assessment in terms of attendance the students are paying more attention to their attending in school. And also to more positive classroom to leading learning outcomes.

Table 4. *Positive Parenting on the academic performance in terms of Behavior*

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Help me boost my self-confidence.	5	SA	1
2. Guide me to do better in school.	4.47	SA	2
3. I set my mind to do better in school.	4.21	SA	5
4. Assist me in improving my attitude towards schooling.	4.33	SA	3
5. Encourage me to maintain my social emotional development	4.32	SA	4
Average Mean	4.46	SA	

Legend: Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1.0-1.80; Disagree (D) = 1.81-2.60 Agree (A) = 2.62-3.40 Moderately Agree(MA) = 3;41-4.20, Strongly Agree (SA) 4.21-5

Table 4 presents the Effect of Positive Parenting on the Academic Performance in terms of Attendance. The highest weighted mean 5, help to boost self-confidence with verbal interpretation Strongly Agree, while the lowest weighted mean 4.21, set my mind to do better in school with the verbal interpretation Strongly Agree.

According to Allison P. According to Danzig, Margaret W. Dyson, Thomas M. Olino, Rebecca S. Laptook, and Daniel N. Klein (2015), children who were highly dysphoric had more difficulty with socially appropriate behaviour as levels of positive parenting increased, whereas low-dysphoric children had less difficulty with socially appropriate behaviour as levels of positive parenting increased. There was also an interaction between positive and negative parenting, with the combination of increased positive and negative parenting predicting children's eventual trouble with socially appropriate behaviour. The findings indicate that positive parenting interacts with early child temperament and negative parenting to influence the development of children's socially appropriate behaviour.

The results of response assessment in terms of Behavior the students is the students is help to boost their confidence. And to approach helps to self and developing the skills.

Table 5. Positive Parenting on the academic performance in terms of Academic Performance

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Help me to do homework.	3.85	MA	4
2. Allot time to help me my project.	3.76	MA	5
3. Guide me to develop good study habit.	4.25	SA	2
4. Encourage me to get good grades.	4.26	SA	1
5. Monitor my studies at home.	3.91	MA	3
Average Mean	4.006	MA	

Legend: Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1.0-1.80; Disagree (D) = 1.81-2.60 Agree (A) = 2.62-3.40 Moderately Agree(MA) = 3;41-4.20, Strongly Agree (SA) 4.21-5

Table 5 presents the Effect of Positive Parenting on the Academic Performance in terms of Attendance. The highest mean 4.26, encourages me to have good grades with verbal interpretation Strongly Agree, while the lowest mean 3.76, allot time to help me to do my projects with the verbal interpretation Moderately Agree.

Khan, Tufail, and Hussain (Citation2014) investigated how parenting styles influence the academic results of postgraduate students in Pakistan and discovered that individuals who grew up with an authoritarian parenting style had no significant association with academic success.

The evidence suggests that the association between parenting methods and academic performance is not necessarily straight, linear, and uncomplicated. Parenting practices have been shown to indirectly effect academic achievement in children through SE and procrastination.

According to the results of respondents assessment in terms of Academic performance the students are paying to encourage their self to get to a high grades and academic performance is show to engaging the performance of school curriculum.

Table 6. Positive Parenting on the academic performance in terms of Communication between Parents and Teachers

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Ask my teacher if I have problem about my studies	3.98	MA	3
2. Volunteer in my class to get updates about my studies.	3.52	MA	5
3. Attend monthly recognition to monitor my grades.	4.15	MA	1
4. Ask my teacher about what ways they can do to improve my grades.	3.95	MA	4
5. Attend PTA meeting to communicate with my teacher regarding my studies.	4.11	MA	2
Average Mean	2.69	MA	

Legend: Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1.0-1.80; Disagree (D) = 1.81-2.60 Agree (A) = 2.62-3.40 Moderately Agree(MA) = 3;41-4.20, Strongly Agree (SA) 4.21-5

Table 6 presents the Effect of Positive Parenting on Academic Performance in terms of Attendance. The highest mean 4.15, to attend monthly recognition to monitor my grades with verbal interpretation Moderately Agree, while the lowest mean is 3.52, Volunteer in my class to get updates about my studies with the verbal interpretation Moderately Agree.

Result shows that according to Abulibcia (2014), a school-based management approach empowers school leaders, teachers, and other stakeholders, including parents, to participate in decision-making, resulting in improved academic performance for students due to increased parental and community participation in their children's education.

The results of communication between parents and teachers and the results of the respondents is to motivate the parent to attending recognition and monitor the grades of their students

Table 7. Summary of table on the “Effect of Positive Parenting on the Academic Performance”

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Attendance	4.39	SA	2
2. Behavior	4.46	SA	1
3. Academic Performance	4.00	MA	3
4. Communication between Parents and Teachers.	3.94	MA	4
Overall Average Weighted Mean	4.19	MA	

Table 7 presents the Summary of the “Effect of Positive Parenting on the Academic Performance. The behavior is the highest indicator with 4.46 weighted mean with the verbal interpretation as Strongly Agree. The lowest indicator about the effect of parenting on academic performance is the communication between Parents and Teachers with 3.94 weighted mean with the verbal interpretation as Moderately Agree.

The evidence suggests that the association between parenting methods and academic performance is not necessarily Given the uneven direct association between se and academic achievement, contemporary researchers are investigating se's mediational function in the relationship between various psychological traits and academic achievement. Yang, Tian, Huebner, and Zhu (2019) found that se plays a mediating role in the link between academic achievement and subjective well-being among Chinese elementary school pupils. Mediated the link between psychological well-being and academic achievement.

Table 8. Significant difference on Effect of positive parenting when grouped according to Age

groups	median	omputed	adjusted value	adjusted freedom	p-value	Signficant Level	Decision
15-16	4.15	15.95471	16.00606	1	0.0001	0.05	REJECT HO
17-18	4.4						

Table 8 Show the Kruskal wallis H test to significant differences in the perceive in the Effects of positive parenting in the academic performance of selected learners in a private school in lopez,quezon when the respondents are classified based on their Age.The computed P-value 0.0001 the critical value is 3.841 with 1 degree of freedom it is also less than of significance level of 0.5. As a results of the null hypothesis is rejected when P- value 0.0001 suggesting that there is significant difference the respondents Grade 10 students regarding the perceived effects of positive parenting on the academic performance

That respondents with age 15-16 and 17-18 years old have the parenting on the academic performance of selected learners in a private school in lopez, quezon

According to the study, any age and gender can have supportive parent Positive parenting is defined as a friendly and supportive interaction between parents and children that promotes individual development (Chakroun-Baggioni et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2021). It is worth noting that there may be a link between positive parenting by both fathers and moms. Zhou et al. (2016) investigated the association between dads and mothers' parenting styles in 896 Chinese teenage homes.

Table 9. Significant difference on Effect of positive parenting when grouped according to Sex

groups	median	omputed	adjusted value	adjusted freedom	p-value	nfcant Le	Decision
FEMALE	4.35	14.59747	14.64106	1	0.0001	0.05	reject ho
MALE	4.15						

Table 9 Show the Kruskal wallis H test to significant differences in the perceive in the Effects of positive parenting in the academic performance of selected learners in a private school in lopez,quezon when the respondents are classified based on their Sex .The computed P-value 0.0001 the critical value is 3.841 with 1 degree of freedom it is also less than of significance level of 0.5. As a results of the null hypothesis is rejected when P- value 0.0001 suggesting that there is significant difference the respondents is Grade 10 students regarding the perceive effects of positive parenting on the academic performance.

That respondent with a Sex female and male have the same respondents of Effects of positive parenting on the academic performance of selected learners in a private school in lopez, quezon

According to Barnett, M.A. and Scaramella, L.V. (2013). Sex disparities in rates of behaviour disorders, including internalising and externalising problems, occur in early childhood. These sex disparities may arise because women parent their sons and daughters differently, or because the impact of parenting on behaviour problems differs between boys and girls.

Conclusions

The conclusion below is based on the findings as summarized.

Most of the respondents who participated were female.

Positive parenting has a direct positive impact on the self-esteem of the learners, under the behavior indicators.

There is no significant difference between on the perceive parenting to the students education when respondents are grouped to age and sex.

It Show that the null hypothesis is reject null. These futher state that positive parenting can provide better learning for students .

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations are forwarded:

For the School Administrators, This will be beneficial to them for they will be able to strengthen the effects of parental involvement on students education .

To the Parents, Parent may frequently communicate to teachers from the benefits of the learners.

To the Teachers, They may teachers task is to teach their students how to be better children and provide their goals.

For the Students, Tey encourage their parents to communicate..

For the Future Researchers, With their teacher to tackle teacher problems about their studies promptly from better results.

References

Abulibcia's (2014) school-based management strategy empowers leaders, teachers, and other stakeholders. <https://doi.org/10.110532org/10.3390/buildings11>

Ahmed ZH Bhutto (2016) parenting has direct positive effects of behavior of students <https://doi.org/10.11/ajpy.12280>

Alandejani and Almadani (2018)student collaboration between parents and teachers <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.9.5.9>

Blair, S. L. (2014). Parental involvement and children's educational performance: A comparison of Filipino and U.S. parents. *Journal of Comparative Family Studies*, 45(3), 351–366

Bartolome and Selangan. (2015). The Reading Profile of Children in the Philippines. *Literacy* <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1207994.pdf>

Basri, Alandejani, & Almadani,(2018). ICT Adoption Impact on Students' Academic Performance: Evidence from Saudi Universities. *Education Research International*, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/1240197>

Bessers S.Chika (2014)), a focus group of parents participated in a workshop that focused on the practice of reading aloud to their children in English in order to examine what parents may do to support their children<https://doi.org/10.1177/146879841559469>

Basser S. Chik A. (2014)- The more parental involvement, the more students are likely to become productive members of society as well as excel in academics. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED577825>

Barnett MA. And Scaramella L.V.(2015) a supportive parents was associated with behavior and to moderate the students <https://doi.org/10.17/S0954579415000759>

Cress well (1994)- Research technique is a Descriptive method of research is together information about the present exiting condition<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7932381>

Castro,De Jesus and SabanL (2018)Parental Involvement and Children's Academic Performance in school liberal Arts and Socio Economic Status *Journal Of Faculty and Students Research University of Immaculatr Conception Davao City*.<https://research.uic.edu.ph/ojs/index.php/arête/articledownload>

Chakroun-Baggioni et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2021). Positive parenting refers to a warm and supportive relationship between parents and children, which serves as a beneficial protective and supportive factor in individual <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1183546>

Dreambos lerning (2013) Parental involvement affects students achievement retrieved January 12,2020 from <https://www.dreambox.com/blog/parentalinvolvement-effects-on-students-educatios>.

Clin Psychol Rev(2014)Positive parenting provide emphirical support for a students [10.1016/j.cpr.2014.04.0003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpr.2014.04.0003).

Eric (2017)- In this way, parental involvement are increased, parents' effort to support ... ERIC Number: EJ1156936. Record Type: Journal. Publication Date: 2017. Pages: 17. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1156936>

Farver et al., 2013, Gonida et al., 2014). Two of its facets, parent goals and parents' academic involvement as perceived by students <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2015.03.011>

Gemma E Derrick (2022)investigate whether the relationship between parents. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-26258-z>

Hayee and Rizvi citation (2017) positive parenting indirectly influence academic performance and to behavior of the child <https://doi.org/10.11/ajpy.12280>

Hayee (2017) positive parenting influences to academic performance <https://doi.org/10.11/ajpy.12280>

Khan Tufail & Hussain (2014) The evidence suggests that the association between parenting methods and academic performance is not necessarily. <https://doi.org/10.111/ajpy.12280>

Leijtene et al. 2017 As a result, it is vital to research attendance rates and their determinants, as well as the impact of parental programming on those who adhere to them. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.child.youth>

Patrishia Padmasari Deka (2016)- shows that children, be it young kids or teenagers, are always hopeful of their parents' support. The emotional, information https://www.researchgate.net/publication/292336897_A_study_on_parental_involvement_in_higher_level_of_education_voices_of_parents_and_students_in_Pub-Kamrup_College_and_Patidarrang_College_Kamrup_district

Sapungan, G. & Sapungan, R. (2014). Parental involvement in children's education: Importance, barriers, and benefits. *Asian Journal of Management Sciences & Education* (Vol. 1, No. 1). Retrieved from: [https://www.ajmse.leena-luna.co.jp/AJMSEPDFs/Vol.3\(2\)/AJMSE2014\(3.2-05\).pdf](https://www.ajmse.leena-luna.co.jp/AJMSEPDFs/Vol.3(2)/AJMSE2014(3.2-05).pdf)

Sheridan, S. M., Knoche, (2016) A randomized trial examining the effects of parent engagement on early language and literacy: The getting ready intervention. *Journal of School Psychology*, 49(3), 361–383. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsp.2011.03.001>

Sales@learning ladders info 2023 help our teachers to teach, help parents to support and help children to learn. <https://www.learningladders.info>

Sea Frey Steinson and ME Farlone (2014) refer above they anyone has concerned with their child <https://positivepsychology.com>. 2014 Jul-Sep; 49(3):200-8. doi: 10.1111/nuf.12093.

Tufail and Hussain (2014) parenting entails positive and negative behavior outcomes and attitudes of achievement of students <https://doi.org/10.11/ajpy.12280>

Vygotsky's Bornstein (2015) Emphasizes parent's role as children first to the teacher, which helps to build their understanding. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov> Volume 13 - 2022

Yang Tian, Huebner and Zhu (2019) discovered that academic achievement is well among the elementary school students. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.51.1.117>

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